

WASTE 4think

MOVING TOWARDS LIFE CYCLE THINKING BY INTEGRATING ADVANCED WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

Ecosolutions:

"NEW ECONOMIC
INSTRUMENTS"

Pay-as-you-Throw
`PAYT` with Radio
Frequency Identification
`RFID` monitoring of
residual waste

SEVESO

"INVOICING SOFTWARE"

Including innovative parameters
to monitor the effectiveness of
RFID readings

"SOCIAL ACTIONS"

Funny sensitization
campaign door to
door

"ZERO WASTE ACTIONS"

Eco-events,
reusable nappies
and virtuous
households contest

A small number of
households will be selected
and undergo a very strict
monitoring to improve their
behaviour to improve waste
reduction.

Objective:

With this innovative actions it is aimed to reach the "theoretical maximum" like 80% of source separation by citizens

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 688995.
The dissemination of results herein reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

WASTE4think.eu

